

LEXICAL-SEMANTIC ISSUES OF MILITARY TERMS OF URDU IN MASS MEDIA TEXT

Lola Ahmadovna Nishanova

Department of South and Southeast Asian Languages, Tashkent
State University of Oriental Studies, Tashkent city

Address: Yunusobod 5-6-40

Phone number: +99890 989 6690

lola.usmanova07@mail.ru

Abstract The article examines the process of lexical-semantic issues of terminological units when used in the mass media text, which appeared due to the rapid development of mass media. The present article considers current military vocabulary borrowed from English to Urdu. The data for the research were collected from authentic materials of popular newspapers such as Daily Pakistan, Daily Jang and the official magazine of Pakistan Armed Forces Hilal.

This article attempts to study the main features of the military terminology of Urdu language. The collected authentic materials were divided into the following semantic groups: terms for military positions, terms for military organizations, abbreviations related to the military sphere, weapons, clothing, words expressing military action and equipment. English loanwords of military terms are used not only in the military, but also in common literary language. Such words have special meaning when they are used in the military. Analysis of English loanwords in semantic groups showed that a lot of words were borrowed in military positions, names of military organizations and abbreviations. We can see that military operations and uniforms semantic group use less English loanwords than other groups.

Based on our analysis, we can predict with a high degree of certainty that it is no coincidence that these borrowings are used in the press. They are available in both bilingual and monolingual dictionaries.

Keywords and phrases: Term, military terminology, English loanword, authentic material, analytical language, grammatical feature, descriptive method, concrete noun, abstract noun.

English has become the leading language in business, science, literature, politics, diplomacy, and many more areas and industries. Since the early 1600s, the English language has had a toehold on the Indian subcontinent. This superiority has had a great impact on all aspects of the socio-economic and political life of all independent countries, including Pakistan. Since the days of British rule in the Indian subcontinent, English has continued to gain official, political and social status and has continued to grow in importance over time.

The privileged role of English can be explained by the importance of the English language in the newspapers which are published in Pakistan. According to the 2019 data of the Pakistan Bureau of Statistics, the total number of newspapers published in the country is 707. 72 of them are published only in English, which is 10.2 percent of all newspapers. The Pakistan Observer, Business Recorder and Dawn are the most popular English language newspapers in Pakistan. 577 Urdu language newspapers are also available in English. Including The Daily Pakistan, Pakistan Times, Daily Qudrat, Daily Global News etc. According to the World Population Review 2021 data, Pakistan is the third most populous English-speaking country after India and the United States. Researching the ongoing relationship between English and local languages of Pakistan has both theoretical and practical implications for the study and teaching of Urdu.

In constant contact with English, local languages in Pakistan, including Urdu, have borrowed many English words and phrases. This process is still actively developing. In recent years, the language situation in the South Asian subcontinent has become the center of attention of world linguists. Many researchers have paid attention to this issue as a lexical material. In their research work, they have expressed many opinions regarding the impact and importance of English on Urdu.

Researchers often focus on the topic of lexicon acquired from English, we can see that several articles have been published on this topic. "Semantic Change in Words Borrowed From English to Urdu" by Aisha Aslam, Lahore, "A Linguistic Study of Borrowings from English to Urdu" by Sipra Muhammad, published in Saudi Arabia Linguistic Study of Words Adopted from Urdu to Urdu). It should be noted that most of these articles are not available for reading. Moreover, the topic of English loanwords in Urdu has not been studied in a coherent and systematic way, in the form of a separate study. Compared to Hindi, it is not difficult to notice that Urdu is more liberal in adopting English loanwords. Linguists and Indologists of different countries have conducted general studies on words that have been borrowed to Urdu from English, but no specific study has been done on lexical acquisitions related to the military field.

Several authentic materials were used in writing a research paper. Daily Pakistan, Daily Jang newspapers and Hilal magazine served as main sources to give examples. The reason for using newspapers and magazines as material can be explained by clear, popular, official information coverage in the mass media.

Daily Pakistan (DP)¹ is a Pakistani newspaper published in both Urdu and English since 1997. Daily Pakistan is a popular newspaper published in major cities of Pakistan like Lahore, Karachi, Islamabad, Multan and Peshawar. The circulation of this newspaper is more than 500,000. Daily Jang (DJ)² is the oldest newspaper of Pakistan in continuous publication since its foundation in 1939. Jang is the top daily newspaper with a circulation of 850,000.

The Uzbek word "harbiy" is derived from the Arabic word harbi: which means "war, army". The word definition is derived from the Latin word "definitio" (definition) and means a short logical content containing the most important features of a particular concept. According to the explanatory dictionaries, the concept of

¹ <https://dailypakistan.com.pk/>

² <https://jang.com.pk/>

definition when applied to "Military term" reflects the following meanings: related to the army, military service; a person in the army, a military employee, a military serviceman; military service, army.³ Apart from these, military weapons, names of military units, military uniforms and military positions are also part of the definition of the military term. The material was collected on the basis of this definition of military terms and the characteristics of the terms borrowed from the English language in Urdu were clarified.

Military terminology is a complex, extremely dynamic object of study and is the most mobile part of the military sublanguage. It consists of different thematic groups. "Thematic group (lexical set) - words that correspond to each other in terms of their basic (root) semantic content, that is, in terms of belonging to the same semantic field".⁴ Based on this definition, military terminology can be understood as a terminology consisting of different thematic groups.

Terms denoting military positions:

Chairman Joint Chiefs of Staff Committee < چیئرمین جوائنٹ چیفس آف سٹاف کمیٹی

چیئرمین جوائنٹ چیفس آف سٹاف کمیٹی جنرل ندیم رضا نے مشترکہ فضائی مشقوں کا معائنہ کیا۔

[DP, 19.12.2020] "Chairman Joint Chiefs of Staff Committee General Nadeem Raza inspected the joint air force exercises".

Commander of Army's Air Defence Lieutenant < کمانڈر آرمی ایئر ڈیفنس لیفٹیننٹ

کمانڈر آرمی ایئر ڈیفنس لیفٹیننٹ جنرل حمودالزمان خان نے مہمانوں کا استقبال کیا۔

[DP, 16.12.2020] "Commander of Army's Air Defence Lieutenant General Hamud Uz Zaman welcomed the guests".

Terms denoting military organizations:

Indian Military Academy < انڈین ملٹری اکیڈمی

اس دوران انہوں نے تعلیم بھی جاری رکھی اور 1932 میں انہیں انڈین ملٹری اکیڈمی میں داخلہ مل گیا۔

³ Annotated dictionary of the Uzbek language. Tashkent. 2006-2008. (online). - P.508.

⁴ Akhmanova O.S. Dictionary of linguistic terms. Moscow, "Sovetskaya entsiklopediya" Publ., 1996. - P.113.

[DP, 24.10.2018] “During this time he also continued his studies and in 1932 he was admitted to the Indian Military Academy”.

آرمی میڈیکل کور < Army Medical Corps

آرمی میڈیکل کور میں تربیت یافتہ ڈاکٹروں اور نرسنگ کے عملے کی کمی کے باوجود مہاجرین کو ہر ممکن طبی امداد اور مہاجر کیمپوں سے وبائی امراض کا سدباب کیا۔

[H, 08.2014] “Despite the lack of experienced doctors and nurses in the army medical corps, all medical care was provided to the refugees and infectious diseases were prevented in the refugee camp”.

سیکیورٹی فورسز < Security forces

سیکیورٹی فورسز کے پہنچنے ہی دہشت گردوں نے فائرنگ کر دی جس کے نتیجے میں ایک جوان نائک نزاکت حسین شہید ہو گیا۔

[DP, 20.06.2021] “As soon as the security forces arrived, the terrorists opened fire and killed soldier Naik Nazakat Hussain”.

Military Abbreviations:

ڈی جی آئی ایس آئی < DG ISI (Director-General of Inter-Services Intelligence)

امریکی وزیر دفاع نے پاکستان میں وزیراعظم شاہدخاقان عباسی، آرمی چیف اور ڈی جی آئی ایس آئی سے ملاقاتیں کیں اور ان ملاقاتوں میں "ڈومور" کا مطالبہ ضرور ہوا ہو گا۔

[H, 01.2018] “The American Defense Minister met with Prime Minister Shahid Khaqan Abbasi, Army Chief and DG ISI in Pakistan and there must have been a demand for "do more" in these meetings”.

را < R&AW, RAW (Research and Analysis Wing)

’را‘ ایجنٹوں کے 50 رکنی دستے کو انڈین ائیر فورس کے ذریعے نکالا گیا۔

[J, 12. 07.2021] “50-strong RAW (Research and Analysis Unit) agents were flushed out with the help of the Indian Air Force”.

آئی ایس پی آر < ISPR (Inter-Services Public Relations)

پاکستانی فوج کے شعبہ تعلقات عامہ (آئی ایس پی آر) کے ڈائریکٹر جنرل میجر جنرل بابر افتخار کا کہنا ہے کہ چین نے افواج پاکستان کے لیے کورونا وائرس کی ویکسین کا عطیہ دیا ہے۔

[J, 08. 02.2021] “Chief of the Pakistan Armed Forces Public Relations (ISPR) Major General Babar Iftikhar has announced that China has donated a vaccine against the coronavirus to the Pakistan Armed Forces.

Military weapons:

Warheads < وارہیڈز

فضا سے فضا اور فضا سے زمینی اہداف کا درست نشانہ لینے والے ہلاک تھری طیارے کو پانچ ہزار کلومیٹر دور تک وارہیڈز کے ساتھ پرواز کرنے میں آسانی ہوگی۔

[DP, 01.10.2018] “The Block 3 aircraft, which can accurately target air-to-air and air-to-ground targets, will be able to fly with warheads up to 5,000 kilometers away”.

Cluster bomb < کلستر بم

بھارتی فورسز نے 30 اور 31 جولائی 2019 کو وادی نیلم میں بذریعہ توپخانہ کلستر بم برسائے، کلستر بموں سے 4 سالہ بچے سمیت 2 شہری شہید جبکہ 11 شدید زخمی ہوئے۔

[DP, 24.09.2020] “On July 30 and 31, 2019, Indian forces dropped cluster bombs in the Neelum Valley with artillery, 2 civilians including a 4-year-old child were martyred and 11 were seriously injured”.

Anti-tank mines < اینٹی ٹینک مائنز

کارروائی کے دوران دس اینٹی ٹینک مائنز بھی برآمد کر لی گئی ہیں۔

[DP, 01.07.2014] “Ten anti-tank mines have also been recovered during the operation”.

Military clothes:

Uniform < یونیفارم

وہ یونیفارم میں ہوتو اسی جذبے کے تحت جان بٹھیلی پر رکھے ملک و قوم کی حفاظت اور خدمت کا فریضہ انجام دیتا ہے

[H, 05.2017] “He carries out the duty of protecting and serving the nation with his life in the palm of his hand in the same spirit even if he is in uniform”.

Helmet < ہیلمیٹ

جبکہ پائلٹ کے ہیلمیٹ میں جدید کنٹرولنگ سسٹم کی وجہ سے پائلٹ کو ٹارگٹ فیئرنگ میں مزید سہولت بھی فراہم ہو جائے گی۔

[DP, 01.10.2018] “Whereas, due to the modern controlling system in the pilot's helmet, the pilot will also be provided with more convenience in target fairing”.

Bulletproof jacket < بلٹ پروف جیکٹ

اس کے گلے میں بلٹ پروف جیکٹ نہیں ہوا کرتی تھی۔

[H, 06.2014] “There was no bulletproof vest around his neck”.

Words related to military actions:

Operations < آپریشنز

اختتامی تقریب میں دونوں ممالک کے دستوں نے اپنی صلاحیتوں اور انسداد دہشتگردی آپریشنز کا مظاہرہ کیا۔

[DP, 19.10.2020] “In the closing ceremony, the troops of both the countries demonstrated their capabilities and anti-terrorist operations.”.

Front line < فرنٹ لائن

جنرل راحیل شریف نے فرنٹ لائن پر لڑنے والے فوجی افسروں اور جوانوں سے ملاقات کی اور آپریشن کے دوران شہید اور زخمی ہونے والے جوانوں کو خراج تحسین پیش کیا ہے۔

[DP, 07.07.2014] “General Raheel Sharif met the military officers and soldiers fighting on the front line and paid tribute to the martyred and injured soldiers during the operation”.

Search operation < سرچ آپریشن

دھماکے کے بعد سیکیورٹی فورسز نے علاقے میں دہشتگردوں کی تلاش کیلئے سرچ آپریشن شروع کر دیا ہے۔

[DP, 02.06.2021] “After the explosion, the security forces have started a search operation to find the terrorists in the area”.

Military equipment:

Gunship helicopter < گن شپ ہیلی کاپٹر

شمالی وزیرستان کے علاقے میران شاہ میں گن شپ ہیلی کاپٹروں کی شیلنگ سے متعدد دہشت گرد مارے گئے۔

[DP, 20.06.2014] “Several terrorists were killed by gunship helicopter shelling in Miran Shah area of North Waziristan”.

Jet aircraft < جیٹ طیاروں

ترجمان آئی ایس پی آر کا کہنا ہے کہ فضائی کارروائی کے دوران جیٹ طیاروں سے بمباری کی گئی۔
[DP, 15.12.2015] “Spokesman ISPR says that during the air operation, jets were
bombarded”.

Radar < ریڈار

پاکستان اور چین کے اشتراک سے تیار کیا جانے والا طیارہ پہلے دونوں بلاکس کے مقابلے میں سستا
بھی ہے اور ٹکنالوجی کے اعتبار سے ریڈار کو دھوکا دینے کی صلاحیت رکھتا ہے۔
[DP, 01.10.2018] “The aircraft, jointly developed by Pakistan and China, is also
cheaper than the first two blocs and is technologically capable of evading radar”.

Analyzing the examples, we can see that the Daily Pakistan used more borrowed words than the official magazine of the Ministry of Defense of Pakistan. The reason, these newspapers are considered as popular publishers, and the scope of the newspaper is wider, it is important that the language of the newspaper is understandable to everyone. Since Hilal, the official magazine of the Ministry of Defense of Pakistan, is a special publication, it covers the views related to the military sector of the country, and it can be noticed that special attention is mainly paid to the national language. Perhaps for this reason, special attention is paid to lexical rules in this official journal. In other words, in this magazine, an attempt was made to use as few English words as possible. Based on this, it can be noted that the attitude of publishers in the country to words borrowed from the English language differ from each other.

We have seen that most of the English borrowings in Urdu belong to the noun group. The noun group is divided into definite and abstract nouns. Among the examples studied above, definite nouns are more commonly used in English acquisitions. These borrowed words correspond in meaning to the meaning of the source language.

As for the adjectives borrowed from English, there were no independently used adjectives. In the examples, we have seen that adjectives participate in the

determining function in the structure of English word combinations. Examples:
Front line < فرنٹ لائن, Bulletproof jacket < بلٹ پروف جیکٹ, Medical Corps < میڈیکل کور“.

Among the collected data, there are several examples of ordinal numbers derived from English as identifiers:

Second lieutenant < سیکنڈ لیفٹیننٹ

سیکنڈ لیفٹیننٹ راشد خان (شہید) 1971 میں کشمیر کے محاذ پر مامور تھے۔

[H, 03.2015] “Second Lieutenant Rashid Khan (deceased) was posted to the Kashmir Front in 1971”.

The descriptive method was used in the process of creating this article. The analysis was performed from a synchronic approach. The method of linguistic description is the main method of linguistics, which consists of systematic inventory of language units, explanation of their structure and practical application.⁵

Linguistic factors play a major role in the derivation process of English words into Urdu because both languages belong to the same language family and are analytical languages from a typological point of view. Each of the analytical languages has its own characteristics. For example, English does not have a grammatical gender category, while Urdu does have a grammatical gender category.

In the age of scientific and technical development, new mechanisms and equipment feel the need to have their own name. The naming process is often related to the English language. However, from a linguistic point of view, they are not purely English words, but are based on Greek-Latin words. Therefore, military words in Urdu are based on such English borrowings, and new ones are constantly being added to this field. In the examples collected by the official magazine "Hilal" of the Ministry of Defense of Pakistan, we can see that English loanwords are used less than in newspapers. In this official journal, it can be seen that the lexical laws

⁵ Akhmanova O.S. Dictionary of linguistic terms. Moscow, "Sovetskaya entsiklopediya" Publ., 1996. - P.225.

of the language are partially followed. Nevertheless, the lexicon of the Pakistani military continues to be open to adopting new English borrowings.

In every sector of Pakistan, English continues to undergo a process of localization, but this process of localization is taking place in each sector separately and in its own way. It is noteworthy that the English words borrowed in the military field are derived to Urdu in a unique way, both phonetically and graphically. The phenomenon of graphic and phonetic doublet was not observed in military English loanwords.

At the beginning of the 20th century, it is clear that the English language had a strong position in the international arena, and that it had a great influence on the languages of the world, including the Urdu language. It is not difficult to notice that Urdu is more open to English borrowings than Hindi. As can be seen from the above examples of English borrowings, there are no strict barriers or objections to the borrowing of words from English into Urdu.

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